

Synagogue at Magdala

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Entry tags: Hellenistic Religions, Archaeological Site, Synagogue, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Ancient Mediterranean, Greek, Unattested, Graeco-Roman, Language, Religious Place, Southern Levant, Jewish Traditions, Judaism, Judaism

A 1st century CE synagogue structure discovered in 2009 at Magdala (Al-Majdal) under the auspices of the Israel Antiquities Authority and the Universidad Anáhuac México Sur. This structure is well decorated and notable for the discovery of a figural stone block within, itself featuring one of the earliest depictions of a menorah. It has at least three rooms, the largest of which is a square hall lined featuring columns and lined with benches. A side room is also lined with benches and has been suggested to have functioned as a study room or bet midrash. Magdala lies on the western shore of the Sea of Galilee, north of Tiberias, and was settled perhaps in the early 2nd century BCE. The town itself was a large settlement by the middle of the 1st century CE. The site boasts archaeological finds from a lavish bathhouse, to quayside, marketplace and richly decorated domiciles. It also features as a prominent town of Galilee in the writings of Josephus. Here under the name Taricheae (with some debate over this identification), Josephus describes the inhabitants are being largely on the side of the Jewish rebels against Rome.

Date Range: 1 CE - 80 CE

Region: Magdala Synagogue

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean

Location of the synagogue structure within the ancient town of Magdala

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Magdala of Galilee: A Jewish City in the Hellenistic and Roman Period. Edited by Richard Bauckham. Waco, TX: Baylor University Press, 2018.
- Source 2: De Luca, Stefano, and Anna Lena. "Magdala/Taricheae." Pages 280–342 in Galilee in the Late Second Temple and Mishnaic Periods. Volume 2: The Archaeological Record from Cities, Towns, and Villages. Edited by David A. Fiensy and James Riley Strange. Minneapolis: Fortress, 2015.
- Source 3: Doering, Lutz. "The Synagogue at Magdala: Between Localized Practice and Reference to the Temple." Pages 127–153 in Synagogues in the Hellenistic and Roman Periods: Archaeological Finds, New Methods, New Theories. Edited by Lutz Doering and 9789004692541_Scales_proof-02.indb 329 15 Jan 2024 5:39:12 pm 330 Bibliography Andrew R. Krause. loudai: Schriten des Institutum Judaicum Delizschianum 11. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2020.

– Source 1: Zapata-Meza, Marcela, Andrea Garza Díaz-Barriga, and Rosaura Sanz-Rincón. “The Magdala Archaeological Project (2010–2012): A Preliminary Report of the Excavations at Migdal.” *Atiqot* 90 (2018): 83–125.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: http://www.hadashot-esi.org.il/report_detail_eng.aspx?id=25336&mag_id=125.

– Source 1 Description: Zapata-Meza, Marcela, and Andrea Garza Díaz-Barriga. “Migdal – 2015: Preliminary Report.” HA-ESI 129 (2017)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2009

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: IAA/UAMS

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Town

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Notes: As far as can be interpreted, there is nothing explicitly significant about the placement of the structure within the settlement.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Part of the settlement of Magdala

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: It can also be considered a social, memorial and political space. While there is no evidence for sacrificial or healing practices, these are at least possible.

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

Notes: There are at least three phases of the structure, suggesting ongoing adaptations.

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes

- ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Collapsed

- ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - As the result of war
 - As the result of pillage

Notes: While uncertain, the structure was perhaps damaged during the First Jewish revolt. The date of the ceiling collapse appears to have been sometime before 80 CE as a coin minted this year was found on top of the collapsed ceiling remains.

- ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Other [specify]: Unclear but likely human-caused. No sign of earthquake

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes

- ↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Partial repair of some features, such as standing columns found within the structure, but not a significant reconstruction.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: YHWH

Notes: This is almost certainly the case but no explicit evidence from the excavated remains.

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: This is perhaps unlikely but within the realms of possibility, depending on how worship is defined.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: Uncertain but likely

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: This is a supposition, once again, there is no clear evidence to be certain but this seems likely.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: There is a strong possibility that scrolls were perhaps used and stored in the structure, but no explicit evidence in favour of such storage and use in this specific structure.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Stone blocks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Frescos painting of "dark red, mustard yellow and blue panels set within black and white frames" - Avshalom-Gorni and Najjar, "Migdal." Also stucco used on columns and mosaic geometric designs.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Stone block found inside with various figural motifs carved on five sides.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Various imagery on the stone block, including menorah and temple paraphernalia.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: Plain painted colours

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Various designs, including meander patterns and rosettes.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Stone block decorated in carved motifs and imagery

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Depending on how the reverse panel of the stone block is understood, which possesses images associated with the divine chariot.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Notes: Depending on how the reverse panel of the stone block is understood, which possesses images associated with the divine chariot.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Imagery associated with the Jerusalem Temple

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: Priestly-elite connections

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Prayer

Notes: If prayer can be understood to be a form of communication

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: Depending on how presence of angels and other entities is understood.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Depending on how presence of angels and other entities is understood.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: This was likely the belief but it is difficult to determine as there is no specific evidence connected to the structure itself.

- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
 - I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Prayer was likely a practice in the structure.

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a good possibility that some kinds of rituals took place, but there is no clear evidence. Remains of immersion pools close by may also be suggestive of particular ritual behaviour associated with the structure.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Notes: There is some discussion as to whether the stone block was involved in collecting and sending offerings to Jerusalem.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Difficult to say if it were for any particular persons, but the structure is much too small to accommodate more than even 10% of the settlement's population.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a possibility, but only for a small group. No clear evidence of such a practice.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a possibility, but only for a small group. No clear evidence of such a practice.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely not, but depending of how this is understood, perhaps.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely not, but depending of how this is understood, perhaps.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– No

Notes: Most likely not but no clear evidence.

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely men, but very unclear. Women were certainly officials in synagogues of late Antiquity.

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a suggestion that the Parables of Enoch were perhaps written in the settlement - Aviam, Mordechai. "The Book of Enoch and the Galilean Archaeology and Landscape." Pages 159-169 in *Parables of Enoch: A Paradigm Shift*. Edited by James H. Charlesworth and Darrell L. Bock. Jewish and Christian Texts in Contexts and Related Studies. London; New York, NY: T&T Clark, 2013.

Bibliography

General References

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Magdala Ashlar" 13 (May 2017). <https://doi.org/10.3828/aj.2017.3>.

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